

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF TUBERCULOSIS BY AGE GENDER, AND TYPE OF TUBERCULOSIS IN DISTRICT KARAK, KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) is a major public health concern both globally and in Pakistan. Understanding the epidemiology of tuberculosis, particularly its distribution by age, gender, and type, is critical for effective control and preventative efforts.

Objective: This study seeks to examine the epidemiological patterns of tuberculosis by age, gender, and type in District Karak, with a particular emphasis on data from 2022 and 2023.

Methods: A retrospective investigation of 6,182 TB patients reported at DHQ Hospital Karak was carried out. The data were divided into three categories: gender, year of registration, and kind of tuberculosis (pulmonary vs. extra-pulmonary). Throughout the study period, the age-specific prevalence of smear-positive patients for both pulmonary and extra pulmonary tuberculosis was determined.

Results: The male-female ratio was practically equal, with 51.15% males and 48.85% females. TB cases were higher in 2023 (53.70%) than in 2022 (46.30%), while infection prevalence was higher in 2022 (34% vs. 29.58%). The overall prevalence of tuberculosis was 31.62 percent. Pulmonary tuberculosis accounted for 77% of cases, much more than extra-pulmonary tuberculosis (23%). Pulmonary tuberculosis was most common in children aged 0 to 4 years (24.97% in 2022 and 15.46% in 2023). Extra-pulmonary tuberculosis showed a similar trend, with the highest frequency in the 0-4 age range (6.16% in 2022 and 7.94% in 2023).

Conclusion: The findings show that pulmonary TB predominates over extra pulmonary TB in District Karak, with a considerable burden in young children. These findings

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highlight the importance of targeted interventions, as well as improved diagnostic and treatment procedures, for combating tuberculosis, particularly in disadvantaged populations.

Keywords: *Tuberculosis, Prevalence, Karak, Pulmonary Tuberculosis, Extra-pulmonary tuberculosis, Mortality, Pakistan.*

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis is a chronic infectious disease caused by the microorganisms *Mycobacterium tuberculosis bacillus* (Koch bacillus), which prefers lung parenchyma and transmits from person to person through inhalation of microorganism-containing particles (1). *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, often known as tuberculosis, infects roughly one-third of the global population (2). In 2009, more than ten million new tuberculosis cases were reported. In the same year, tuberculosis killed over a million HIV-negative people (3). The vast majority of new tuberculosis infections arise in developing countries, accounting for more than 85% of all reported cases (3).

Tuberculosis alone is responsible for more fatalities in women of reproductive age than all-cause maternal mortality (4). Historically, the advent of HIV caused a threefold increase in the frequency of various types of tuberculosis in countries with a high HIV prevalence; however the incidence of tuberculosis has recently dropped, as reported in 2009. Tuberculosis is responsible for 25% of AIDS-related mortality in HIV-positive patients, and it killed up to 0.4 million HIV-positive people globally in 2009. HIV-positive patients with *Mycobacterium TB* infection are 20-30 times more likely to have active tuberculosis than HIV-negative patients.

The situation is aggravated by multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, or MDR. In 2009, there were approximately 0.5 million new cases of MDR worldwide (4). 86% of the world's MDR TB infections occur in 27 countries, with Pakistan ranked fourth among these high-burden nations (3). In a recent study conducted in Mumbai, MDR-TB patients and their families described the condition as the worst of the worst illnesses, with the treatment being worse than the illness itself (5).

According to the World Health Organization, individuals with tuberculosis and MDR-TB are growing progressively resistant to at least isoniazid and rifampicin each year, which is the principal barrier to disease elimination. A recent meta-analysis of data from 25 countries revealed that MDR patients had a combined therapy success rate of only 61%, compared to 82% for drug-susceptible persons. This is the main reason for the increase in MDR-TB cases. According to the WHO, 9 million people worldwide contracted tuberculosis in 2013, and 1.5 million died as a result (6). Since 1945, all available anti-TB methods have resulted in a 45% reduction in tuberculosis fatalities; nonetheless, the disease has been treated by programmatic, directly monitored therapeutic short course strategies. MDR-TB is entirely the product of human error, which includes inaccurate diagnosis, inefficient treatment, ignorance of the illness, failure to appropriately care for TB patients, extended wait times, and disobedience, particularly in terms of anti-TB medication adverse effects (6).

In 2010, there were 9.8 million incident cases (128 cases per 100,000 persons), with an additional 1.1 million HIV positive patients. In 2010, India had the highest incident reports (2.0-2.5 million), followed by China (0.9-1.2 million), South Africa (0.40-0.59 million), Indonesia (0.37-0.54 million), and Pakistan (0.33-0.48 million) (7).

India and China account for 38% of all cases (26% in India, 12% in China). South Africa and Swaziland have the highest tuberculosis rates, with one new case per 100 people each year (8). In 2010, Asia reported 59% of tuberculosis cases, with Africa accounting for 26%, the Eastern Mediterranean for 7%, Europe for 5%, and the Americas for 3% (7). In 2012, Asia accounted for 58% of TB cases, followed by Africa (27%), the Eastern Mediterranean (8%), Europe (4%), and the Americas (3%).

A 2017 study in Pakistan found 27000 MDR-TB cases, with 4.2% newly infected and 16% having previously had TB treatment. The first National Drug Resistance Survey in Pakistan, completed in September 2013, found that the frequency of new cases of pulmonary tuberculosis was 3.7%, while the prevalence of retreatment patients was 18.1%. This shows that due to previous poor anti-TB therapy, a lack of patient adherence, and poor/inadequate TB drug quality in Pakistan, retreatment patients are more

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common than non-retreatment patients. According to the WHO in Pakistan, instead of starting them on a Category II regimen, patients who fail medication, such as those in Category 1, should be evaluated for drug resistance (9). Our current study's purpose is to investigate the prevalence of tuberculosis patients at the District Karak KhyberPakhtunkhwa.

Material and Method

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the District Head Quarter Hospital in District Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The National Tuberculosis Control Program Pakistan (NTCP) funds the hospital, which treats tuberculosis patients. The sputum microscopy laboratory services and tuberculosis drug regimen are congruent with the methods of the National Tuberculosis Control Program. From January 1, 2022 to December 31, 2023, 6182 suspicious patients were investigated. A retrospective study was designed. Sputum smear microscopy was carried out utilizing the Ziehl-Nelson staining method. A positive smear resulted in a positive tuberculosis diagnosis, whereas a negative smear resulted in a negative diagnosis. Demographic information about the patients was gathered, including their age, gender, types of tuberculosis, and previous medical history.

Result

In the current study, 6182 patients with tuberculosis were recorded at DHQ Hospital Karak, with a male to female ratio of 51.15% and 48.85% as shown in figure 1 (1). In 2022 the male to female ratio is 492(50.56%) and 481(49.44) while in 2023 508(51.73%) respectively. A higher number of patients were registered in 2023 than in 2022 as 53.70% and 46.30% respectively as shown an figure 1 (2). A high prevalence of tuberculosis infection was reported in 2022, with 34% of the population being infected, and in 2023, with 29.58% of the population being infected.. The overall prevalence of tuberculosis positive infection was reported to be 31.62 percent as shown an figure 1 (3).

Figure:1 The figure presents the male to female ratio and prevalence of tuberculosis at DHQ Hospital Karak for 2022 and 2023, highlighting a higher number of cases and prevalence rates in 2023 compared to 2022.

In 2022 Age-wise analysis of the pulmonary sputum in smear positive cases revealed that the highest number of cases (24.97%) was recorded in age 0-4 years, followed by 9.36% in age 5-14 years, 6.17% in age ≥ 65 years, 6.16% in age 25-34 years, 6.07% in 15-24 years, 6.06% in both age group 45-54 years and 55-64 years, and 4.72% in 35-44 years.

Age-wise analysis of the extra pulmonary sample in smear positive cases revealed that the highest number of cases (06.16%) were recorded in age 0-4 years, 5.73 in age 45-54 years, followed by 3.70% in age 55-64 years, 3.28% in age 5-14 years, 3.09% in 25-34 years, 2.98% in age 35-44 years, 2.78% in age 15-24 years, and 2.67% in ≥ 65 years as shown an Figure 2.

In 2023 Age-wise analysis of the pulmonary sputum in smear positive cases revealed that the highest number of cases (15.46%) was recorded in age 0-4 years, followed by 9.57% in age 15-24 years, 7.44% in age 5-14 years, 7.33% in age 25-34 years, 7.03% in ≥ 65 years, 5.30% in age 45-54 years 4.59 in age 35-44 years, and 4.49% in 55-64 years.

In 2023 Age-wise analysis of the extra pulmonary sample in smear positive cases revealed that the highest number of cases (07.94%) were recorded in age 0-4 years, 4.58 in age 45-54 years, followed by 2.65% in

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age ≥ 65 years, 2.54% in age 15-24 years, 2.45% in 5-14 and 25-34 years, 2.35% in age 35-44 years, as shown in Figure 2.

Age-wise Analysis of Pulmonary and Extra-Pulmonary TB in Smear Positive Cases (2022 vs 2023)

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Figure: 2

Pulmonary tuberculosis is 77% more common than extra-pulmonary tuberculosis, which is 23%.

Discussion

The current study found an infection rate of 31.62% in the general population of District Karak. The total prevalence rate in our study is lower than in earlier studies [10-12]. Shams et al. [10] found a 33.08% prevalence of tuberculosis infection in District KharBajaur Agency. A study done in the specified area of District Dir (Lower) found that the overall prevalence rate was 34.71% [11]. Ahmad et al. [12] observed a 36.82% prevalence of tuberculosis in District Dir (Lower).

In our study, 70% of individuals with pulmonary tuberculosis had positive sputum smears. According to a 2011 WHO report, out of 270,394 registered cases of tuberculosis in Pakistan, 105,733 were sputum smear positive and 103,824 were sputum smear negative, indicating that about half of new pulmonary infections were smear positive [13]. In a 2010 research from Poland, 40.1% of cases of pulmonary tuberculosis tested positive for sputum smear [14].

In our study, 30% of patients suffered from EPT. In 2011, 45 537 (16.84%) of the 70 394 total notified cases of tuberculosis were extra pulmonary, with females being impacted more than males [13]. EPT has become more common as HIV infection spreads over the world, especially in industrialized nations such as the United States, where it accounts for 10- 15% of tuberculosis cases [15].

The current study also presents a detailed age-based analysis of pulmonary and extra-pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) cases in District Karak for 2022 and 2023, demonstrating major trends that reflect the region's TB demographic burden.

In both years, pulmonary tuberculosis was notably more common than extra pulmonary tuberculosis, accounting for 77% of cases. This is consistent with global data that pulmonary tuberculosis is the most prevalent type in endemic areas (16). The age distribution of smear-positive pulmonary tuberculosis cases revealed that the youngest age group (0-4 years) had the largest disease burden in both 2022 (24.97%) and 2023 (15.46%). This trend highlights young children's sensitivity to tuberculosis, possibly due to underdeveloped immune systems and greater exposure risks in households with active TB cases (17).

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Notably, the percentage of cases in this age range decreased from 2022 to 2023, potentially due to advances in early detection, preventive measures, or vaccination coverage.

The age categories 5-14 years and 15-24 years also accounted for a significant burden of pulmonary tuberculosis, with more cases among adolescents and young adults in 2023 than in 2022. This could be due to higher exposure risks in communal settings like schools and workplaces, as well as delays in healthcare access (18). In senior age groups (≥ 65 years), the burden of pulmonary tuberculosis remained significant, especially in 2022 (6.17%) and 2023 (7.03%). This is consistent with previous research, which found that the elderly are more susceptible to tuberculosis due to immunosenescence, comorbidities, and diagnostic delays (19).

Extra-pulmonary tuberculosis (EPT) had a similar age distribution but was less frequent overall, consistent with global trends (World Health Organization, 2011). In both years, the 0-4 age group had the largest proportion of EPT cases (6.16 percent in 2022 and 7.94 percent in 2023). This highlights children's susceptibility to extra pulmonary symptoms, which could be caused by hematogenous dissemination of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (20). Furthermore, the 45-54 age group had a greater proportion of EPT patients in both years, which could be attributed to concomitant diseases such as diabetes or HIV that impair immune function (21).

The discovered findings indicate that TB control efforts in District Karak should focus on early detection and treatment of susceptible groups, particularly young children and the elderly. Diagnostic capacities for extra pulmonary tuberculosis must also be improved, as its elusive appearance frequently results in delayed treatment. Furthermore, focused community awareness efforts for middle-aged and young adult populations should help to reduce rising tuberculosis rates in these groups.

Finally, this study focuses on the demographic and clinical problems of tuberculosis in District Karak, emphasizing the importance of targeted therapy. Enhanced monitoring, early diagnosis capabilities, and public health education are critical for lowering the TB burden in this region.

Conclusion

This descriptive cross-sectional study conducted at DHQ Hospital Karak reveals a large prevalence of tuberculosis throughout a two-year period, from 2022 to 2023. The study found a male-to-female ratio of 51.15% and 48.85%, with a significant increase in instances in 2023 compared to 2022. An age-based research revealed that the youngest age groups, notably those aged 0 to 4, had the highest prevalence of both pulmonary and extra-pulmonary tuberculosis. The overall prevalence of tuberculosis-positive infections was recorded as 31.62%, with pulmonary tuberculosis being 77% more common than extra-pulmonary tuberculosis. These findings highlight the continuous tuberculosis burden and the need for improved diagnostic, treatment, and preventive efforts in the region.

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